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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO ASSESS THE KAP
PATTERN (KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE)
ABOUT AN ONSET OF BLEEDING GUMS AMONG SCHOOL
GOING CHILDREN**¹Kashfa Akram, ²Ambreen Akram, ³Hamna Manzoor¹Dental Section Allied hospital Faisalabad, ²Hamdard University Dental Hospital Karachi,³Dental Section Allied Hospital Faisalabad.**Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

This cross-sectional research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (September 2017 to March 2018) to assess the KAP (Knowledge, Attitude and Practices) of school going children about the onset of bleeding gums. The outcomes show that awareness level was satisfactory as 74% of students were well aware of the bleeding gums; whereas, 26% were not. Bleeding gums was an issue faced by 63% of the children; whereas, the dentist was consulted by 51% of the students. Few of the students relied on homemade remedial action or ignored the issue at all. On the basis of results, we conclude that the awareness level of students was good about oral health, associated effects and bleeding gums.

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INTRODUCTION:

In the consideration of dental health, the focus is on the prevention of teeth cavities and dental caries. We also need to put emphasis on the oral cavity supporting structures and gingiva. Dental health mainly depends on the role of gingiva along with overall wellbeing of oral health.

Inadequate oral maintenance leads to an onset of bacteria buildup that leads to plaque. The advanced shape of plaque is tartar which irritates the gums and causes inflammation and swelling of the gums also called gingivitis. If the situation continues it may shape into an even worse situation called periodontitis. With the development and progression of the disease, tissues of the gums become deteriorated and damaged. In this state, the anchoring of the teeth is disturbed and it can result in the shape of tooth loss. Adults do face tooth loss because of gums disorders [1].

Patients often do not take seriously the issue of Bleeding gums; however, it can possibly be dangerous and alarming as it can indicate serious diseases and disorders such as bleeding complexities [2]. A number of research studies also show a relation between preterm birth and severe gum disease issues [3].

Generally, various factors contribute to it which include non-maintenance of oral health, bacterial infection, poor nutrition, bleeding disorders, hard brushing, trauma, hormonal changes, deficient vitamin K, anticoagulant medications intake, dental flossing improper technique, dengue fever, hot food, pregnancy and scurvy & chemicals [4 – 6]. The objective of this particular research was to assess the KAP (Knowledge, Attitude and Practices) of school going children about the onset of bleeding gums.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (September 2017 to March 2018) to assess the KAP (Knowledge, Attitude and Practices)

of school going children about the onset of bleeding gums. The research sample included 150 children who were in the age bracket of (14 – 16) years. Students were randomly selected from different schools. We did not include any student with the palate, cleft theft and congenital defects along with the history of allergy and other systemic diseases of primary nature.

We assessed the KAP pattern of the children about bleeding gums through a self-designed questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed among students for possible feedback and experience. A pilot study led the complete project in which we distributed the questionnaire initially among ten percent of the students. No student faced any difficulty in the completing of the provided questionnaire. Every student gave his consent to participate in the research before the commencement of the research study. Every student was also explained in detail about the objective of this particular research protocols.

RESULTS:

The outcomes show that awareness level was satisfactory as 74% of students were well aware of the bleeding gums; whereas, 26% were not. Bleeding gums was an issue faced by 63% of the children; whereas, the dentist was consulted by 51% of the students. Few of the students relied on homemade remedial action or ignored the issue at all. Various causes of bleeding gums were unbalanced diet (17%), not maintaining oral hygiene (25%); whereas, 58% did not know the causative factors of the disease. Suffering students also considered dentist's consultation (75.5%); whereas, rest did nothing for the proper management of the disease.

Among 63% bleeding gums students about 51% went to the dentist for the treatment of the bleeding gums. Remaining students relied on home-made remedies or even neglected bleeding gums at all. Detailed outcomes analysis is given as under:

Table: Awareness Regarding the Term Bleeding Gums

	Details	Percentage
Awareness	Yes	74.00
	No	26.00
Opinion – I	Unaware	58.00
	Poor Oral Hygiene	24.00
	Imbalance Diet	18.00
Opinion – II	Yes	75.50
	No	24.50

DISCUSSION:

Multiple national and international research studies have also demonstrated the various satisfactory KAP pattern among school going children about the vitality of oral hygienic health in the perspective of improved age [9, 10]. The practice of oral hygiene has no direct association with the awareness about oral hygiene. This problem is faced by underdeveloped countries as a major issue [11]. There is a need to create an environment of professional and public awareness about the healthy society concept in the general public for systemic and oral illnesses [12]. The key responsibility of educating and spreading awareness about oral health lies on the shoulders of educators and schools [13, 14]. The base of the children's oral health attitude depends on the acquired information and experience from various sources such as print media, electronic media, teachers and parents [15].

As an analysis of the outcomes, we conclude that education has a vital role to play to decrease and diminish the issue of bleeding gums. There is a need to educate children about the bleeding gums and its

associated factors through good oral health practices, brushing techniques and precautionary measures. It will build the capacity of the teachers to counter the effects and causes of the bleeding gums on personal and social health.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of results, we conclude that the awareness level of students was good about oral health, associated effects and bleeding gums.

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